

Dermaptera (Insecta), identified by A. Brindle and preserved in the collections of the National Museum of Natural History (Sofia)

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Abstract: The National Museum of Natural history in Sofia stores a collection of 30 species of earwigs (Dermaptera) from Nepal, Sri Lanka, Nigeria and other countries, identified by A. Brindle 30 years ago. Many other Dermaptera (unidentified) are also housed at the museum.

Key Words: Dermaptera, Museum, Nepal, Nigeria, Sri Lanka, Brindle

In the 1970s I contacted Dr. Alan Brindle (Manchester) who agreed to identify the collection of Dermaptera, brought by me from many countries (Nigeria, Cameroon, Equatorial Guinea, Canary Islands, Tanzania, DR Congo, Nepal, Burma, Thailand, Sri Lanka, Bolivia, Brazil, Peru, Papua New Guinea and others) and preserved now in the National Museum of Natural History in Sofia. Dr. Brindle (1915 – 2001) was one of the leading world specialists in Dermaptera. Despite his retirement in 1982, he tried to work also on part of our collection and returned most of the material in Sofia. He published one new species from Nigeria (*Diplatys beroni* BRINDLE, 1982), but the remaining material was left unpublished.

It might be useful to publish the identifications made by Dr. Brindle, to commemorate the prominent British entomologist and to inform the specialists that the Museum harbours 30 identified species from many countries, and that some unidentified material is still waiting for someone willing to undertake the work unfinished by Dr. Brindle.

Meanwhile, after the correspondence with Dr. Brindle I have collected many other Dermaptera, also preserved in the Museum (unidentified). Some of this material came from Ecuador, Morocco, Indonesia, Malaysia, Nepal, Cuba, Mexico, Sicily,

Sardinia, North Korea, Vietnam, the Dominican Republic, Peru, Brazil, Bolivia, Papua New Guinea, DR Congo, Zambia, Zimbabwe, Mozambique, Nigeria, Tanzania, Uganda, Sudan, and the Balkan countries. This list does not include the entire Dermaptera material of the Museum, as there are also many earwigs from Bulgaria and the Balkans identified by other specialists.

As the identifications by Dr. Brindle were done by 1985, I tried to actualize the names taking into account the changes meanwhile.

Abbreviations: P.B. – Petar Beron, S.A. – Stoitsev, V.B. – Vladimir Beshkov

Dermaptera in Sofia Museum, collected by P. Beron and identified by A. Brindle

Protodermaptera
Pigydicranoidea
Fam. Diplatyidae
Diplatyinae

Diplatys beroni Brindle, 1982 – Nigeria (P.B.):
Jos, Plateau State, Sept.1976 (Holotype ♂); same data (Allotype ♀); Jos, July 1976 (1 ♀ Paratype), 5.10.1976 (1 ♂ Paratype)

Diplatys sp. – many from Nigeria and Nepal.
Eudermaptera
Forficuloidea

Fam. Chelisochidae

Chelisochinae

Chelisoches morio (Fabricius, 1775) – Papua New Guinea (P.B.): West New Britain Prov., Kimbe Bay, 13.11.1975 (♀)

Fam. Forficulidae

Allodahliinae

Allodahlia scabriuscula (Audinet-Serville, 1838) – Nepal (P.B.): Dhaulagiri Zone, Chumra Village, 1500 – 1800 m, 10.10.1984 (1 ♀)

Diaperasticinae

Diaperasticus erythrocephalus (Olivier, 1791) – Nigeria (P.B.): Kaduna State, 17.10.1978 (1 ♂); Plateau State, Pandam Wildlife Park, July, 1977 (2 ♂), 1.10.1978, at light (21 ♂, 25 ♀), 11.20.1977 (f); Wase Rock Game Reserve, 19.09.1978 (1 ♂)

Diaperasticus wittei Hincks, 1955 – Nigeria (P.B.): Kaduna State, 17.10.1978 (1 ♂)

Forficulinae

Forficula auricularia (Linnaeus, 1758) – Canary Islands (P.B.): Gran Canaria: Cruz de Tejada, 23.8.1988 (♂, ♀)

Forficula beelzebub (Burr, 1900) – Nepal (P.B. leg.): Langtang Valley, Lama Lodge, 2500 m, 25.9.1984 (♀); Kali Gandaki Valley, Kagbeni, 2800 m, 28.10.1984 (♀); Dhaulagiri Zone, Marpha, 2600 – 2700 m, 21.10.1984 (♂, ♀); Dhaulagiri Zone, Tukuhe, 21.10.1984 (♂, ♀); from Dana to Ghasa, 1400 – 2000 m, 19.10.1984 (P.B.)(♂, ♀); Dhaulagiri Zone, Landrung, 1500 – 1600 m, 0.10.1984 (♂, ♀); Anapurna, above Bhichuk, 1600 – 1700 m, 8.10.1984 (P.B., S.A.)(♂, ♀)

Forficula senegalensis Audinet - Serville, 1839 – Nigeria (P.B. leg.): Plateau State, Wase Rock Game Res., 4.09.1978, at light (10 ♂, 14 ♀); 19.09.1978 (1 ♀); Kano State, Kano Zoo, 4.10.1978, fluorescent light (13 ♂, 11 ♀); Maiduguri, 24.10.1976; Jos, Sept. 1976; 15 km N Akwanga, 14.08.1976 (1 ♂)

Forficula schlagintweiti (Burr, 1904) – Nepal (P.B., S.A.): Langtang, 17.09.1984, 3500 – 3600 m (♀); from Hinko to Machhapuchhre Base Camp, 3000 – 3800 m, 16.10.1984 (♀)

Guanchia sjoestedti (Burr, 1907) – Tanzania (P.B., V.B.): Kilimanjaro, below Horombo Hut, 3200 – 3780 m, 4.09.1983 (2 ♂, 1 ♀)

Guanchia triangulata (Hincks, 1950) – Tanzania (P.B., V.B.): Kilimanjaro, below Horombo Hut, 3200 – 3780 m, 4.09.1983 (5 ♂, 1 ♀, immat.)

Opisthocosmiinae

Cordax formosus (Burr, 1905) – Nigeria (P.B.): Plateau State, Pandam Wildlife Park, 1.10.1978 (1 ♀)

Eparchus simplex (de Bormans, 1894) (identified as *Eparchus oberthuri* Borelli, 1912) – Nepal

(P.B., S.A.): Langtang Valley, 16.9.1984, Khanjung – Sharpugaon, 2225 – 2600 m (1 ♂)

Syntonus neolobophoroides (Burr, 1901) [as *Obelura*] – Sri Lanka (P.B.): Pidurutalagala, 2100 – 2400 m, 28.11.1984 (1 ♂)

Fam. Spongiphoridae (= Labiidae)

Spongiphorinae (= Homotaginae)

Homotages feae (de Bormans, 1888) – Nepal (P.B., S.A.): Pokhara trek, above Bhichuk, 800 m, 8.10.1984 (♂); above Bhichuk, 1600 – 1700 m, 8.10.1984 (♂)

Labiinae

Labia minor (Linnaeus, 1758) – Nigeria (P.B.): Plateau State, Jos, 1350 m, 25.05.1978 (1 ♀); Jos, 1300 m, 1300 m, 5.11.1976 (♂, ♀); Pandam Wildlife Park, at light, 1.10.1978 (12 ♂, 15 ♀); 21.07.1977

Paralabella curvicauda (Motschulsky, 1863) – Equatorial Guinea (Fernando Po) (P.B.): 5 km W Malabo, 29.12.1976 (♂, ♀)

Plesiodermaptera

Labiduroidea

Fam. Labiduridae

Labidurinae

Forcipula decolyi de Bormans, 1900 – Nepal (P.B., S.A.): Langtang Nat. Park, Grang, 28.09.1984 (1 ♀)

Forcipula sp. – Nepal (P.B., S.A.): Langtang Valley, Khanjung, 2200 m, 15.09.1984

Labidura riparia (Pallas, 1773) – Sri Lanka (P.B., S.A.): Polonaruwa, 23.11.1984; Nigeria (P.B.): Plateau State, Pandam Wildlife Park, at light, 1.10.1978 (2 ♀); Jos, 1350 m, 3.11.1978 (1 ♂), Pai River Game Res., 3.09. (1 ♂); Bauchi State, Yankari Game Reserve, Wikki Camp, 14.01.1978 (2 ♂, 1 ♀); Maiduguri, 24.10.1976 (♂)

Nalinae

Nala lividipes (Dufour, 1828) – Burma: (P.B., S.A.): Rangoon (Yangon), 6.11.1984 (♀); Sri Lanka (P.B., S.A.): Dambulla, 24.11.1984, 25.11.1984 (♂, ♀); Polonaruwa, 23.11.1984 (♂, ♀)

Metadermaptera

Anisolabidoidea

Fam. Anisolabididae

Anisolabidinae (=Carcinophorinae)

Aborolabis nepalensis (Brindle, 1974) – Nepal (P.B.): Dhaulagiri Zone, Landrung, 1500 – 1600 m, 9.10.1984 (♀, immat.); Ghasa-Lete (2000 – 2450 m), 20.10.1984 (♀, immat.); Anapurna trek, 910.1984, Dhampus to Landrung (immat.); Anapurna trek, above Bhichuk, 1600 – 1700 m; Kathmandu, 1700 m, 1.09.1984 (immat.)

Anisolabis felix Burr, 1907 – Tanzania (P.B., V.B.): Kilimanjaro, below Horombo Hut, 3200 –

3780 m, 4.09.1983 (1 ♀, 4 immat.)

Anisolabis kudagae Burr, 1901 - Sri Lanka (P.B.): Nuwara Elyia, 1900 – 2100 m, 28.11.1984 (♂, ♀)

Anisolabis sp. – Sri Lanka (P.B., S.A.): Kandy, 26.11.1984 (♀, immat.)

Canarilabis maxima (Brullé, 1838) – Canary Islands, Tenerife (P.B.): Puerto de la Cruz, 20.8.1977 (♀)

Euborellia annulipes (Lucas, 1847) – Canary Islands, Tenerife (P.B.): Puerto de la Cruz, 0-800 m, 20.8.1977 (8 ♀)

Euborellia cincticollis (Gerstaecker, 1883) – Nigeria (P.B.): Plateau State, Pandam Wildlife Park, at light, 1.10.1978 (2 ♀); Plateau State, Pandam

Wildlife Park, 21.7.1977 (♀)

Euborellia compressa (Borelli, 1907) – Cameroon (P.B.): 70 km NE Nanga Eboko, 2.01.1977

Gonolabis electa Burr, 1910 - Sri Lanka (P.B.): December, 1984 (1 ♂, 1 ♀)

Gonolabis nigeriensis (Brindle, 1978) – Nigeria (P.B.): Plateau State, Jos, 1350 m, 25.05.1978 (1 ♂)

Paradermaptera

Apachyoidea

Fam. Apachyidae

Apachyinae

Apachyus beccarii Dubrony, 1879 – Papua New Guinea, New Ireland (P.B.): Lenkamin Village, under bark, 2.12.1975 (1 ♀)

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Dermaptera (Insecta), определени от A. Brindle и депозиранни в колекциите на Националния природонаучен музей (София)

Петър БЕРОН

(Резюме)

Част от колекциите от Dermaptera на НПМ (София) бяха определени от A. Brindle (Manchester), но останаха непубликувани (30 вида, главно от Непал, Нигерия и Шри Ланка). Тук даваме тяхния списък (материалите бяха върнати в НПМ), както и списък от страни, от които в Музея се пазят неопределени материали.